

A systematic review of measurement instruments applied skin and nail of the foot

Ruiz-Muñoz M.¹_{ABCDEF}, Cuesta-Vargas A.I.^{1,2}_{ABCDAEF}, Kunde L.²_{ABCDEF},

¹ Faculty of Health Sciences. University of Malaga. Malaga Spain.

² School of Clinical Sciences of Faculty of Health at Queensland University Technology, Australia.

Received 29.09.2016, Accepted 26.11.2016

Abstract

The aim of this article is to complete a systematic review of patient reported outcomes measures (PROM) and outcome measures (OM) applied to the skin and nail of the foot. A database search of MEDLINE, EMBASE, CINAHL, PEDRo, PUBMED and SCOPUS for English language articles published between 1995 and 2015 was conducted, focussing on articles that provided validity or reliability data. Two independent reviewers completed the study selection, quality appraisal and data extraction. The Critical Appraisal Skills Programme Español tool (CASPe) was used to assess the study quality. Studies that did not meet inclusion criteria or were not focused on skin or nails were excluded. 496 articles were reviewed. After the successive stages of exclusion, only studies 11 were relevant to this revision. Each of the 11 articles displayed a similar threat to validity, relating to likelihood ratios, operator blinding and responsiveness. A comparison between the different questionnaires showed good agreement across a range of aspects of methodological quality. This review concludes that both kinds of instruments (PROM and OM) provide an accurate and reliable method to measure the health status of the skin and nails.

Keywords: podiatry, reliability, patients report outcomes, outcome measurements.

Introduction

The use of patient reported outcome measures (PROM) quantify the patient's condition and meet the evidence-based medicine, in addition to this their use is becoming more common in clinical practice [1]. It is well known that it is important to use a standardized methodology and this should be disseminated and improving existing measures and develop new ones only when necessary [2]. PROM have been used to assess the effect of therapeutic interventions targeted at people with foot and ankle pathology and their impairment and disability by researchers and clinicians [3].

Outcome measures (OM) are objective tests that require the presence of an examiner and direct observation [4]. Objective measures development of the functional capacity has provided clinicians and researchers a method to compare outcomes between subjective perception (self-reported) and objective measure [5]. OM have established validity and reliability in their development, therefore, should be used and incorporated in any research study to provide greater confidence in the results.

There are various studies that have evaluated the prevalence of foot disorders in different populations. The prevalence of orthopaedic problems with foot disorders in a European population study was 20.4% [6]. The prevalence of foot disorders according to another study was 24% being the toes and forefoot most common anatomical sites of pain and disability [7]. Other studies conclude that 10% of the population showed a foot incapacitating pain and over 80% had problems during walking [8].

An important project conducted in more than 17 countries, 52.5% of patients had some aspect of their quality of life affected by their foot diseases. Specifically, 30.7% of patients experienced pain, 40.3% had discomfort in walking, 19.6% had limited his daily activities and 27.3% were embarrassed [9].

Problems caused by fungi and caused by diabetes are highly studied for their impact on the feet and its measurement generates great interest. Fungal infections are the most common and its prevalence increases with age. 10% of the population suffers this pathology and

40% of cases affect the nails [10]. In patients with diabetes prevalence of foot ulcers ranges between 1.3% and 4.8% [11].

Despite the great diffusion of PROM and OM between the clinician and researcher and the relevance of the results that both provide, there is a high heterogeneity among the instruments applicable to podiatric patients, furthermore, the methodological quality and the great variability, limit the comparison or generalization of results [12].

With the purpose to balance the absence of an updated systematic review that can be a guide to clinicians and researches to select the appropriate instrument this work was conducted. The aim of this study is to complete a systematic review of PROM and OM applied to the skin and nail of the foot.

Methods

Study selection

Literature search focused on the retrieval of published studies indexed in the following electronic databases: MEDLINE, EMBASE, CINAHL, PEDRo, PUBMED and SCOPUS. Search terms included validation studies, reproducibility of results, podiatry and foot diseases, these general keywords were chosen to reduce the possibility that any study that meets the inclusion criteria and the level of validity and reliability could be excluded although that meant it would be greater the number of results obtained and therefore the number of studies to review. The search was limited to English language, hu-

mans and the last 20 years (1995-2015) (Figure 1). To be included in this review, studies had to meet the criteria outlined below.

Studies were excluded if they were not primary studies, if title or abstract did not include the keywords, if they did not support any validity and reliability data or if they were not focused on skin or nails.

Title and abstracts identified by the initial search strategy were screened to identify potentially eligible reports and retrieve full-text articles. When title or abstract did not clearly indicate whether an article should be included, the complete article was obtained and reviewed.

Type of study

Studies that develop tools aimed at the nail or dermal diagnosis of the foot and provide acceptable validity and reliability data.

Data extraction

Two independent reviewers completed data extraction with a consensus opinion. A standardized data extraction tool was constructed to identify and detail key features of each study. About psychometric properties, for PROM studies the extracted study details were instrument description, measuring object, content validity, construct validity, criterion validity, responsiveness and reliability and for OM studies were instrument description, measuring object, sensitivity, specificity, gold standard and reliability dies.

Table 1 Keywords and filters		
Podiatry	Skin	Reproducibility of results
Human		
Published year: 1995 to 2015		
Language: English and Spanish		

Table No 1. Data extraction

Assessment of study quality

Two independent reviewers completed the quality appraisal, disagreements resolved by consensus. Studies were critically appraised using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme español (CASPe) tool [13].

Results

Study selection

The initial search strategy provided 496 studies which were reduced to 62 relevant studies after title and inclusion criteria review. After abstract and CASPe (score >5) review, a total of 11 studies met the criteria for further evaluation by this review, Figure 2 shows selection flowchart.

Methodological quality

Methodological quality as scored on the CASPe can be found in Table 1. There were no irresolvable disagreements between authors. All 11 studies included in this review scored greater than five so this tool has been an elimination criterion. Frequently, accuracy of the results was absent and the most of the studies failed to score for evaluation blinded and for the calculation of likelihood ratios.

Psychometric properties

The responsiveness in PROM and reliability in OM studies were more frequently missing data during the extraction studies details. In terms of construct validity, this study highlights the lack of confirmatory analysis; only previous exploratory analyses were presented. A summary of the studies can be found in Table 2 and 3.

Table No 2. Selection flowchart

PRO	Gold Standard	Description of the sample	Description of the experiment	Evaluation blinded	Neutrality in the results	Likelihood ratios	Accuracy of the results	Reproducibility of the test	Validity of the test	Influence of the results	Total score
Lubeck DP, Gause D, Schein JR, et al. (1999)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	8
Drake LA, Patrick DL, Fleckman P, et al. (1999)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	7
Vileikyte L, Peyrot M, Bundy C, et al. (2003)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	7
Price P, Harding K (2004)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	7
Warshaw EM, Foster JK, Cham PMH, et al. (2007)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	7
Ortonne JP, Baran R, Corvest M, et al. (2009)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	7
Ecemis T, Degerli K, Aktas E, et al. (2006)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	8
Foto JG, Brasseaux D, Birke JA (2007)	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	7
T Entolouris N, Achtsidis V, Marinou K, et al. (2007)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	10
Monteiro-Soares M, Dinis-Ribeiro M (2010)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	10
Thompson N, Gordey L, Bowles H, et al. (2013)	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	8

Table No 3.. Methodological quality

STUDY	INSTRUMENT DESCRIPTION	MEASURING OBJECT	CONTENT VALIDITY	CONSTRUCT VALIDITY	RESPONSIVENESS	GOLD STANDARD	RELIABILITY
Lubeck DP, Gause D, Schein JR, et al. (1999) HRQoL onychomycosis	64 items questionnaire with 13 scales: general health perceptions, health transition, pain, social functioning, mental health, health distress, physical function, toenail symptoms, appearance problems, physical activities problems, overall problems, stigma and treatment satisfaction	Impact of toenail onychomycosis on health-related quality of life	Others scales and patients	Interscale correlations: generic scales correlated moderately (0.27-0.57) and weakly with disease-specific scales (-0.12-0.25) Discriminant validity: Statistically significant differences between males and females and between patients under 65 years and older	Improved group: responsive to clinical change in greater part of the scales Stable group: no statistically significant changes	Clinical diagnosis of onychomycosis	ICC= 0.52 - 0.89 α = 0.76 - 0.93
Drake LA, Patrick DL, Fleckman P, et al. (1999) Toenail onychomycosis QoL questionnaire	17 items questionnaire with 3 components: social, emotional and symptoms	Impact of onychomycosis on patients' quality of life (toenail version)	Interviews with patients and expert panel	Discriminant validity: Variation in QoL according to country, age and gender No significant relationships between QoL and duration or extent of onychomycosis or the n° of nails involved. Significantly correlated with QoL scores (only with respect to the extent of nail involvement)		Patients diagnosed by dermatologists	ICC= 0.80 α = 0.70 (symptoms scale α = 0.6)
Vileikyte L, Peyrot M, Bundy C, et al. (2003) NeuroQoL	43 items with several domains: painful symptoms and paresthesia, symptoms of reduced/lost feeling in feet, diffuse sensory motor symptoms, limitations daily activities, interpersonal problems and emotional burden	Patients' perceptions of the impact of diabetic peripheral neuropathy and foot ulcers on their quality of life	Literature review, expert panel and interviews with patients	Good convergent and discriminant validity: factor loadings= 0.60 (items hypothesized factor) NeuroQoL was more powerful than the SF-12 in mediating the relationship between QoL and neuropathy		Vibration Perception Threshold (VPT) and Neuropathy Disability Score (NDS). Criterion validity: NeuroQoL subscales were more strongly associated than SF-12 measures with NDS and foot ulcers	α = 0.86-0.95 Correlation between NeuroQoL physical and psychosocial scales: r= 0.39-0.67

STUDY	INSTRUMENT DESCRIPTION	MEASURING OBJECT	CONTENT VALIDITY	CONSTRUCT VALIDITY	RESPONSIVENESS	GOLD STANDARD	RELIABILITY
Price P, Harding K (2004) CWIS	26 items questionnaire with 3 scales: Physical symptoms and everyday living (12 items), Social life (7 items) and Well-being (7 items)	Impact of chronic wounds (leg ulcers and diabetic foot ulcers) on patient health-related quality of life (HRQoL)	Focus group and individual interviews	Factor analysis: 3 factors contained 26 items and explain 51% of the variance	Ability to discriminate between different health states (t-test in the 3 months, $P < 0.001$)	CWIS and SF-36: Physical symptoms ($r = 0.53$, $P < 0.0001$), Social life ($r = 0.47$, $P < 0.0001$) and $r = 0.56$, $P < 0.0001$) and Well-being ($r = 0.217$, $P = 0.01$ and ($r = 0.332$, $P < 0.0001$)	Test-retest: high level of reproducibility ($P < 0.001$) $\alpha = 0.77-0.96$
Warsaw EM, Foster JK, Cham PMH, et al. (2007) NailQoL	39 QoL (modified Skindex-29 questions and 10 additional nail-specific questions)	Burden of skin disease for patients with onychomycosis	Patients and others questionnaires	Pearson correlation coefficient comparing regression factor (RF) scores and unweighted hypothesized scale scores Symptom RF1: 0.21*, RF2: 0.95*, RF3: 0.08, Function RF1: 0.02, RF2: 0.11, RF3: 0.98*. Emotion: RF1: 0.95*, RF2: 0.29*, RF3: 0.07 * $P < 0.01$	Statistically significant better NailQoL scores were found in individuals with complete cure ($P < 0.01$) 18 months	Culture-proven onychomycosis	ICC to Symptom, Function and Emotion subscales: 0.88, 0.90, 0.91 α to Symptom, Function and Emotion subscales: 0.80, 0.29, 0.92
Ortonne JP, Baran R, Corvest M, et al. (2009) NPQ10	10 items and unidimensional questionnaire to address physical aspects	Impact of nail psoriasis on patients' QoL	Patient association and experts in dermatological research and on QoL	PCA One component accounted for 49% of the total variance	NPQ10 score is significantly higher ($P < 0.0001$) in patients with dual location (hands and feet) of nail involvement	NPQ10 and DLQI: Good agreement between both scores. Coefficient correlation = 0.48	Test-retest: Intra-group coefficient = 0.82 $\alpha = 0.88$

Table No 4. PRO psychometric properties

STUDY	INSTRUMENT DESCRIPTION	MEASURING OBJECT	SENSITIVITY SPECIFICITY	GOLD STANDARD	RELIABILITY
Ecemis T, Degerli K, Aktas E, et al. (2006)	Direct microscopic examination. Growth in Culture.	Tinea pedis	Direct microscopy Se: 95 % Sp: 69,6%	Culture (consistency of 79.2% between the culture and direct examination)	
Foto JG, Brasseaux D, Birke JA (2007)	9 infrared thermometers instruments used in peripheral neuropathy	Dermal skin temperatures			Pearson correlation coefficients >0.989 (temperature change measurements made by the two testers)
Tentolouris N, Achtsidis V, Marinou K, et al. (2008) IPN	Test assessing sudomotor dysfunction	Peripheral neuropathy in diabetes	Se=0.87(95% CI0.81-0.92) Sp= 0.66 (0.58 – 0.73) Positive predictive value=0.94 (0.90 – 0.97) Negative predictive value= 0.79 (0.72- 0.85).	Neuropathy symptoms score and Neuropathy disability score (IPN diagnostic more cases of Peripheral neuropathy than both scores)	Agreement between patient and health care provider of the IPN: k= 0.88 (95% CI, 0.85– 0.91)
Monteiro-Soares M, Dinis-Ribeiro M (2010)	Boyko’s model variables (HbA1c, visual impairment, monofilament insensitivity, tinea pedis, onychomycosis, and history of foot ulcer and amputation) and others variables (physical impairment, reported myocardial infarction and stroke, educational level, vascular disease, foot care habits)	Predict foot ulceration in patients with diabetes	Se (95% CI), sp (95% CI), LR+ (95% CI), LR– (95% CI) NHR Original model: 84 (75-90) 70 (65-75) 2.83 (2.34-3.47) 0.23 (0.14-0.36) NHR Optimised mode: 88 (80-93) 74 (68-79) 3.36 (2.74-4.16) 0.16 (0.09-0.28)	The optimised model had a higher AUC (0.88, 95% CI 0.84–0.91) than the original model (0.83, 95% CI 0.78–0.88)	
Thompson N, Gordey L, Bowles H, et al. (2013) PWAT	Assessment tool designed to assess the status of wounds based on a 2-dimensional visual image	Status of wounds		Digital Image versus Bedside Assessment: ICC= 0.60-0.95 (95% CI)	Intrarater: ICC = 0.52-0.93. Test-retest: ICC= 0.86-0.90. Interrater: ICC = 0.71.

Table No 5. OM psychometric properties

Abbreviations list of the tables: AUC: area under curve; CI: confidence interval; CWIS: Cardiff Wound Impact Schedule; DLQI: Dermatology Life Quality Index; HRQoL: Health-related Quality of Life; ICC: intraclass correlation coefficient; IPN: indicator plaster neuropad; k: kappa; LR: likelihood ratios; NailQoL: Nail Quality of Life; NeuroQoL: Neuropathy and Foot Ulcer Specific Quality of Life; NHR: next to highest risk; NPQ10: Nail psoriasis quality of life scale; PCA: principal component analysis; PWAT: photographic wound assessment tool; Se: sensitivity; Sp: specificity; α : Cronbach alpha coefficient .

Discussion

This review is focused on diagnostic tools aimed at skin and nail assessment with foot application. These tools can be resolved by the clinician (OM) or by the patient (PROM).

It was identified 11 instruments, 6 of them were PROM that had evidence to support their use. In the same way, the other 5 tools were OM provided by physical examination.

Instruments with evidence to support the 5 categories of content, construct, criterion and clinical validity and reliability allow a more comprehensive interpretation of the obtained scores. Four instruments [14–17] had evidence for all of these categories.

In PROM studies, the highest score in the checklist CASPe was obtained to the tool developed by Lubeck DP and collaborators (1999). The remainder of the studies scored 7, having deduction of points in sections of "Likelihood Ratios" and "Accuracy of the results". OM studies obtained generally a higher score. Trials developed by Tentolouris N and collaborators (2008) [18] and Monteiro-Soares M and Dinis-Ribeiro M (2010) [19] achieved the maximum score.

All the studies included in PROM classification bar one were questionnaire related QoL (quality of life) with more than one dimension and the number of items were greater than 20. The exception is the NPQ10 scale

that assessed only physical aspects (one-dimensional) and had a number of 10 items.

The most common dimensions were pain, disability and health status. Three of the scales were aimed at patients with onychomycosis; one, at patients affected by psoriatic nail and two, at patients affected by diabetic neuropathy.

All the studies showed content validity (literature review, interviews with patients and Expert panel) and construct validity in their development; the estimation used mostly is convergent/divergent validity. The criterion validity was carried out with other scales already recognized as gold standard or patients previously diagnosed.

Instruments that had evidence to support their use among subjects with different conditions (responsiveness) include NPQ10; CWIS; NAILQoL and HRQoL onychomycosis, which studied different groups of individuals according to their health and different periods of time.

The tools implemented by Drake LA and collaborators (1999) [20] and Vileikyte L, and collaborators (2003) [21] did not show responsiveness data.

The reliability was moderate to high in all of the studies although those that showed the best data are NeuroQoL and NailQoL. Test-retest and internal consistency were calculated in all cases.

Regarding the *OM studies*, two tools focus on diabetic neuropathy [18-19], one measured skin temperature [22], other foot fungal infection [23] and the last one, the status of wounds [24]. The sensitivity and specificity were calculated for each of the studies with the exception of the study by Foto JG and collaborators (2007). The values were greater than 0.84 for sensitivity and 0.66 for specificity. The gold standard used were others scales or diagnostic tests.

Reliability was calculated for the instruments defined by Foto JG and collaborators (2007) and Tentolouris N. and collaborators (2007) with high values (>0.88).

It is known that foot disorders affect the quality of life. Moreover, the prevalence of these disorders is very high. PROM and OM are extending in clinical practice to diagnostic and assess these pathologies. All instruments included in this review appeared to have a reasonable amount of time commitment required for patient completion and for clinician scoring (reproducibility of the test).

This current systematic review offers a guide to clinicians and researches to select the appropriate instrument.

References

1. Gabel P., Burkett B., Yelland M. Balancing fidelity and practicality in short version musculoskeletal patient reported outcome measures. *Physical Therapy Reviews*, 2009; 14: 221.
2. Coste J., Guillemin F., Pouchot J. et al. Methodological approaches to shortening composite measurement scales. *J Clin Epidemiol*, 1997; 50: 247.
3. Martin RL., Irrgang JJ. A survey of self-reported outcome instruments for the foot and ankle. *Journal of Orthopaedic and Sports Physical Therapy*, 2007; 37: 72.
4. Reuben DB., Siu AL. An objective measure of physical function of elderly outpatients. *J Am Geriatr Soc*, 1990; 38: 1105.
5. Loewenstein DA., Argüelles S., Bravo M. et al. Caregivers' judgments of the functional abilities of the Alzheimer's disease patient: a comparison of proxy reports and objective measures. *J Gerontol B Psychol Sci Soc Sci*, 2001; 56: 78.
6. Burzykowski T., Molenberghs G., Abeck D., et al. High prevalence of foot diseases in Europe: results of the Achilles Project. *Mycoses*, 2003; 46: 496.
7. Thomas MJ., Roddy E., Zhang W. et al. The population prevalence of foot and ankle pain in middle and old age: A systematic review. *Pain*, 2011; 152: 2870.
8. Garrow AP., Silman AJ., Macfarlane GJ. The Cheshire Foot Pain and Disability Survey: a population survey assessing prevalence and associations. *Pain*, 2004; 110: 378.
9. Katsambas A., Abeck D., Haneke E. et al. The effects of foot disease on quality of life: results of the Achilles Project. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*, 2005; 19: 191.
10. Roberts DT., Taylor WD., Boyle J. Guidelines for treatment of onychomycosis. *British Journal of Dermatology*, 2003; 148: 402.
11. Boulton AJM., Vileikyte L., Ragnarson-Tennvall G., et al. The global burden of diabetic foot disease. *Lancet*, 2005; 366: 1719.
12. Terwee CB., Bot SDM., De Boer MR. et al. Quality criteria were proposed for measurement properties of health status questionnaires. *J Clin Epidemiol*, 2007; 60: 34.
13. CASPe Critical Appraisal Skills Programme Español [Internet]. <http://www.redcaspe.org/drupal/>
14. Lubeck DP., Gause D., Schein JR., et al. A health-related quality of life measure for use in patients with onychomycosis: a validation study. *Qual Life Res*, 1999; 8: 121.
15. Price P., Harding K. Cardiff Wound Impact Schedule: the development of a condition-specific questionnaire to assess health-related quality of life in patients with chronic wounds of the lower limb. *Int Wound J*, 2004; 1: 10.
16. Warshaw EM., Foster JK., Cham PMH. et al. NailQoL: a quality-of-life instrument for onychomycosis. *Int. J. Dermatol*, 2007; 46: 1279.
17. Ortonne JP., Baran R., Corvest M., et al. Development and validation of nail psoriasis quality of life scale (NPQ10). *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*, 2010; 24: 22.
18. Tentolouris N., Achtsidis V., Marinou K. et al. Evaluation of the self-administered indicator plaster neuropad for the diagnosis of neuropathy in diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 31: 236, 2008.
19. Monteiro-Soares M., Dinis-Ribeiro M. External validation and optimisation of a model for predicting foot ulcers in patients with diabetes. *Diabetologia*, 2010; 53: 1525.

20. Drake LA, Patrick DL, Fleckman P. et al. The impact of onychomycosis on quality of life: development of an international onychomycosis-specific questionnaire to measure patient quality of life. *J. Am. Acad. Dermatol*, 1999; 41(2 Pt 1): 189.
21. Vileikyte L, Peyrot M, Bundy C. et al. The development and validation of a neuropathy- and foot ulcer-specific quality of life instrument. *Diabetes Care*, 2003; 26: 2549.
22. Foto JG, Basseaux D, Birke JA. Essential features of a handheld infrared thermometer used to guide the treatment of neuropathic feet. *J Am Podiatr Med Assoc*, 2007; 97: 360.
23. Ecmis T, Degerli K, Aktas E, et al. The necessity of culture for the diagnosis of tinea pedis. *Am. J. Med. Sci*, 2006; 331: 88.
24. Thompson N, Gordey L, Bowles H. et al. Reliability and validity of the revised photographic wound assessment tool on digital images taken of various types of chronic wounds. *Adv Skin Wound Care*, 2013; 26: 360.

Corresponding Author:

Cuesta-Vargas A. I.
Faculty of Health Sciences. University of Malaga.
Arquitecto Francisco Peñalosa St, 3.
29010. Málaga (Spain).
phone+34 951952852.
E-mail: acuesta@uma.es.

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.